

1 **Prostaglandin biosynthesis genes are therapeutic targets in cardiovascular disease.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 East Islip, NY USA 11730
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death in humans. We recently identified chemokine
7 ligands CCL7 and CCL18 as therapeutic targets in cardiovascular disease. We report here identification
8 of genes that function in prostaglandin biosynthesis, *PTGER2* and *PTGR1*, as mediators of disease
9 pathology in processes culminating in myocardial infarction (heart attack). In the foam cell, the cellular
10 building block of the plaque, expression of *PTGR1* *PTGER2*, and *PTGDS* was activated, while in the
11 carotid plaque itself, *PTGDS*, *PTGS1*, *PTGER4* and *PTGER2* were activated. Prostaglandin biosynthesis
12 genes are therapeutic targets in cardiovascular disease.
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2 PTGER2

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